

EFFECT OF *Moringa oleifera* LEAF EXTRACTS ON GROWTH PERFORMANCE AND ECONOMICS OF BROILER CHICKENS

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to evaluate the influence of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts on growth performance and economics of broiler chickens. A total of 250-day-old broiler chicks (Vencobb-430) were randomly distributed into five groups with 5 replicates of 10 birds in each. Different dietary treatments were; basal diet with no supplement (NC- negative control) and basal diet supplemented with antibiotics (PC-positive control), aqueous extract of 1.5% Moringa powder (MOAQE), ether extract of 1.5% Moringa powder (MOEE) and alcoholic extract of 1.5% Moringa powder (MOALE). The result showed that Moringa extract supplemented group have significantly higher body weight gain as compared to negative control group during finisher phase. Overall body weight gain is also significantly higher in Moringa supplemented group as compared to control group and numerically higher than positive control. Profit per birds is significantly higher in aqueous and alcoholic Moringa extract supplemented group as compared to control group. Thus, Moringa extracts can be used as growth stimulator in broiler birds.

Key words: Broiler; Extract, Body Weight Gain, Economics and Moringa.

Introduction

The poultry farming is an important source of animal protein and its meat is cheaper as compared to goat and fish meat. Harmful infectious agent can easily infect broiler chickens with weak immune system, resulting to huge losses in poultry farming. The use of antibiotic is discouraged due to antimicrobial resistance and antibiotic residue in meat. Now people are ready to pay higher price for organic meat and eggs due to health awareness among them. So, there is urgent need of natural herbs to promote health and performance of broiler chickens. Herbs were recommended to increase metabolic process and improve health status of livestock (Panagasa *et al.* 2012). *Moringa oleifera* is such an herbal plant with multiple utility as every part of plant has beneficial effects. The unique features of *M. oleifera* are its richness in proteins, carbohydrates and fibres with low fat. The leaves have been reported to enclose a range of essential amino acids and are a good source of alpha linoleic acid (Moya *et al.* 2011). The most used parts of the plant are the leaves, which are rich in vitamins, carotenoids, polyphenols, phenolic acids, flavonoids, alkaloids, glucosinolates, isothiocyanates, tannins and saponins (Leone *et al.* 2015). *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts have been renowned as having anticancer, cytotoxic, antiproliferative, anti-leukemia, anti-hepatocarcinoma and chemo-protective properties. (Berkovich *et al.*, 2013). *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract was reported to improve growth rate and feed conversion ratio in supplemented birds (Paul *et al.* 2018). Aqueous *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts supplementation resulted in higher body weight and lower FCR in broiler birds (Albi *et al.* 2017). Significantly better final body weight, average body gain and FCR were reported among groups enriched with aqueous and alcoholic extract of *Moringa oleifera* leaf in comparison to birds on basal diets (Hussein and Jassim, 2019). Best values of net revenue, economic efficiency and relative economic efficiency were noted in birds supplemented with Moringa extract in litre drinking water compared with control and other treatment groups (AbouSekken, 2015). Partial replacement of fish meal with Moringa leaf meal reduces the feed cost and also improved the economics for broiler production (Zanu *et al.* 2012). The net profit per bird was highest in Moringa supplemented groups and lowest value for control (Meshram *et al.* 2019). In view of above background, the aim of present study was to investigate the effects of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts as dietary supplement on growth performance and economics of broiler birds.

Materials And Methods

For conducting the present experiment an approval from “Institutional animal ethical committee (IAEC)” was obtained vide reference number IAEC/CVSc/P-36/2019. A total of 250 one-day old Vencobb-430 strain chicks were randomly allocated into five dietary treatment groups with 5 replicates of 10 chicks in each group. The chicks were kept on five dietary treatments which includes a basal diet without any additive in negative control (NC) or that supplemented with antibiotics (Positive control-PC), aqueous extract of 1.5% Moringa powder (MOAQE), ether extract of 1.5% Moringa powder (MOEE) and alcoholic extract of 1.5% Moringa powder (MOALE) in basal diet. Birds were fed *ad libitum* in different phases of experimental trial.

The chicks were kept on deep litter system under uniform standard management conditions with availability of clean, fresh and wholesome drinking water. Individual body weight (BW) at zero day and weekly interval was recorded upto 35 days of experimental trial. Replicate-wise feed intake (FI) of chicks was recorded at weekly interval and from these data body weight gain (BWG) was calculated accordingly. At the end of research trial, economic return was also calculated to search out the commercial viability of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts supplementation in broiler production.

The data were analysed under completely randomized (CRD) by employing one way analysis of variance (Snedecor and Cochran, 1994) and means of different dietary treatments were compared with Duncan multiple range test. The P value less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Results And Discussion**Growth Performance**

The data pertaining to the growth performance of broilers in terms of body weight gain are presented in Table 1. The result showed that the body weight gain of PC and MOAQE group birds were significantly ($P<0.05$) higher than NC group during prestarter phase. Starter period had recorded similar weight gain among different groups. In finisher phase PC and Moringa extract treated groups recorded significantly ($P<0.05$) higher weight gain in comparison to NC group birds. The overall weight gain of Moringa extract supplemented groups was found significantly ($P<0.05$) higher NC group but statistically similar to PC group birds. Similar trends were also observed for daily weight gain.

The present findings of better body weight gain of broilers due to Moringa leaf extracts supplementation are in agreement with the reports of Alabi *et al.* (2020), Esiegwu (2019) and Faluyi and Agbede (2018) who reported significantly ($P<0.05$) higher final body weight, body

weight gain in Moringa aqueous extract supplemented broiler chickens in comparison to control group birds. Hussein and Jassim (2019) and Tete et al. (2013) also recorded significantly ($P<0.05$) higher body weight gain with alcoholic and aqueous extract of *Moringa oleifera* as compared to control group broiler chickens. The present results are in

line with the findings of Paul et al. (2018) and Allam et al. (2016) who studied the supplementation of aqueous extract of *Moringa oleifera* in broiler birds and observed significantly ($P<0.05$) body weight gain in supplemented group in comparison to control group.

Table 1 Effects of dietary supplementation of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts on weekly body weight gain (g) of broiler chickens

Attributes	NC	PC	MOAQE	MOEE	MOALE	P-value
First week	138.97±1.97 ^a	145.82±1.61 ^c	143.70±1.44 ^{bc}	137.41±1.30 ^a	139.44±1.42 ^{ab}	0.001
Second week	379.37±1.62 ^a	277.04±3.24 ^a	277.88±1.73 ^a	294.88±4.24 ^b	288.38±3.31 ^b	<0.001
Third week	453.57±1.28	450.52±10.11	477.14±9.27	466.90±10.67	470.68±10.21	0.291
Fourth week	525.10±7.81 ^{bc}	535.12±8.78 ^c	504.28±8.02 ^{ab}	497.02±7.88 ^a	515.84±10.93 ^{ab}	0.017
Fifth week	346.16±6.00 ^a	390.84±11.63 ^b	423.42±10.60 ^c	438.54±13.17 ^c	427.30±9.15 ^c	<0.001
Pre-Starter	138.97±1.97 ^a	145.82±1.61 ^c	143.70±1.44 ^{bc}	137.41±1.30 ^a	139.44±1.42 ^{ab}	0.001
Starter	732.94±11.44	727.55±11.80	755.02±10.64	761.78±13.44	759.06±12.20	0.138
Finisher	871.26±9.75 ^a	925.96±18.38 ^b	927.70±13.53 ^b	935.56±16.08 ^b	943.14±10.98 ^b	0.003
Overall	1743.18±16.83 ^a	1799.33±30.12 ^{ab}	1826.42±20.91 ^b	1834.75±27.78 ^b	1841.64±20.91 ^b	0.027

Values with different small letter superscripts in a row differed between groups significantly ($P<0.05$).

The improvement in body weight gain of birds fed Moringa extract supplement diets could be attributed to digestion enhancing properties and stimulation of growth favouring bacteria like other herbal drugs while, decreasing harmful microorganisms and also influence the gut microflora of broiler birds.

Economics

The economics of broiler production kept under different feeding treatments are presented in Table-2. The total feed cost of group NC, MOEE and MOALE was found significantly ($P<0.05$) higher than PC and MOAQE group birds. The feed additive cost of MOEE group was highest among the different groups. All extract treated groups showed significantly ($P<0.05$) higher additive cost in comparison to NC and PC group broilers. The total expenditure was also significantly ($P<0.05$) higher in MOEE (Rs.155.52) and MOALE (Rs.153.14) group as

compared to control (Rs.146.71) while PC (Rs.142.49) and MOAQE (Rs.142.56) group had significantly less values. Sale price per bird of Moringa extract supplemented groups was significantly ($P<0.05$) higher than NC group but statistically similar to PC group birds. The profit of PC and MOAQE group birds was found significantly ($P<0.05$) higher than MOEE, MOALE and NC group birds.

In agreement to our finding AbouSekken (2015) reported improvement in the average values of net revenue due to feeding broiler low protein diet supplemented with Moringa leaf extracts compared with control and other experimental groups. Portugaliza and Fernandez (2012) conducted a study to determine the growth performance of Cobb broilers supplemented with MO aqueous leaf extract and also observed significantly higher ($P<0.01$) return of investment in Moringa extract treated group than the control group.

Table 2 Effects of dietary supplementation of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts on economics of broiler chickens

Attributes	NC	PC	MOAQ	MOEE	MOAE	P-value
Chick cost (Rs. /bird)	45	45	45	45	45	
Feed cost (Rs. /bird)	95.71±1.07 ^b	90.88±0.90 ^a	90.35±0.91 ^a	94.97±0.88 ^b	94.25±1.06 ^b	<0.001
Feed additive cost (Rs. /bird)	0.00±0.00 ^a	0.61±0.006 ^b	1.21±0.01 ^c	9.54±0.09 ^c	7.89±0.09 ^d	<0.001
Miscellaneous cost (Rs. /bird)	6	6	6	6	6	
Total expenditure (Rs. /bird)	146.71±1.07 ^b	142.49±0.90 ^a	142.56±0.92 ^a	155.52±0.97 ^c	153.14±1.15 ^c	<0.001
Sale price per bird	161.85±1.55 ^a	166.93±2.75 ^{ab}	169.35±1.91 ^b	170.16±2.54 ^b	170.78±1.90 ^b	0.027
Profit (Rs. /bird)	15.14±0.79 ^a	24.45±1.87 ^b	26.79±1.15 ^b	14.65±1.65 ^a	17.64±1.03 ^a	<0.001

Values with different small letter superscripts in a row differed between groups significantly ($P<0.05$).

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